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Modeling early events in HIV-1 infection using pseudovirion in 293T.

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We used a pseudovirion HEK293T cell culture system to model and study early events in HIV-1 infection in vitro.

Citations

1. Harrich, D., Ulich, C., García-Martínez, L.F. and Gaynor, R.B., 1997. Tat is required for efficient HIV-1 reverse transcription. The EMBO journal, 16(6), pp.1224-1235.

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